

Synthesis of 2,2'-Imino-Bis Thiazoles

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A number of 2, 2'-imino-bis thiazoles were prepared using Hantzsch thiazole synthesis by condensing 2-haloketone with thiazolyl thiourea.

BIS THIAZOLE unit has been found to occur in a number of antibiotics like micrococcin, saramycin and bleomycin¹⁻⁶. This unique system, which constitutes the backbone of these compounds is believed to play an important role in the biological activities of these natural products. It was, therefore, thought that the synthesis of such compounds would be an interesting problem in continuation with our study of potentially active sulphur compounds. This paper is, therefore, devoted to the preparation of 2,2'-imino-bis-4,4'-(substituted phenyl)-thiazoles.

All the title compounds described in this work, were synthesised by following Hantzsch thiazole synthesis, from the corresponding 2-haloketones and the thiazolyl thioureas. This method was preferred to dithiobiuret⁷ method and Ullman type condensation⁸, because of the absence of any six reactions, and of good yields. Moreover, thiazolyl thioureas are important intermediates in that they are likely to possess activity⁹.

Following 2-haloketones and substituted thioureas were used for the preparation of 2,2'-iminobis thiazoles

(A) 2-Haloketones

- (1) 2, 4'-Dichloro acetophenone
- (2) 2, 3', 4'-Trichloro acetophenone
- (3) 2, 2', 5'-Trichloro acetophenone
- (4) 2, 2'-Dichloro-5-methyl acetophenone
- (5) 2'-Bromo-5'-methyl-2-chloro acetophenone
- (6) Ethyl- α -chloro aceto acetate

(B) Thiazolyl thioureas

- (1) 1-(2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) thiourea
- (2) 1-(2-(4-p-chlorophenyl thiazolyl)) thiourea

- (3) 1-(2-(4-(2'-Hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl)-thiazolyl)) thiourea

2-Haloketones (1-5) were prepared from the corresponding hydrocarbons using Friedel and Craft's method, whereas ethyl- α -chloroaceto acetate was prepared by chlorinating active methylene group with sulphuryl chloride¹⁰

Thiazolyl thioureas were prepared from the 2-amino thiazoles by following Kurzer's method¹¹

Condensation of 2-haloketone with thiourea in the presence of alcohol gave smoothly 2,2'-iminobis thiazole hydrochloride, which upon basification with ammonium hydroxide solution yielded the free base (Fig. 1). The formation of these compounds was confirmed from their elemental analysis (Table 1).

2,2'- Iminobis - 4,4'-disubstituted thiazole

Fig 1

TABLE I—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF 2, 2'-IMINOBIS THIAZOLES

Compound No	2, 2'-Iminobis thiazoles (only 4 and 4'-substituents are given)	M P °C	Molecular formula	Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
				Required	Found	Required	Found
1	4-(2'-Chloro 5' methyl phenyl)-4'-(p chlorophenyl)-	202	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	54.54	55.68	3.11	3.55
2	4-(phenyl)-4'-methyl 5'-carbethoxy-	210	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	55.65	55.64	4.34	4.44
3	4-(4'-Chlorophenyl)-4'-methyl 5'-carbethoxy-	198	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ ClO ₂ S ₂	50.67	50.97	3.68	3.06
4	4-(2'-bromo 5'-methyl phenyl)-4'-(p chlorophenyl)-	195	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ BrClS ₂	49.29	50.50	2.81	3.01
5	4-(3', 4'-Dichlorophenyl)-4'-phenyl-	145	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	53.47	54.08	2.72	3.41
6	4-(3', 4'-Dichlorophenyl)-4'-(p-chlorophenyl)-	155	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ Cl ₃ S ₂	49.26	49.90	2.28	2.55
7	4-(2', 5'-Dichlorophenyl)-4'-(p-chlorophenyl)-	200	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ Cl ₃ S ₂	49.26	50.08	2.28	3.12

Experimental

Preparation of 2,2'-iminobis thiazoles

A mixture of 2-haloketone (0.01 mole), substituted thiazolyl thiourea (0.01 mole) and alcohol (25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for about two hours. The solid thus separated was filtered and washed with ether to remove unreacted ketone and thiourea. It was then boiled with water and ammonia solution whereby free base was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetone.

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